

An Alternate Explanation for the Name Pu of Envoys from Sanfoqi to the Song Dynasty in the “The Tributors”

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In 1968 the Princeton University Art Museum acquired an album containing eight leaves with depictions of tribute bearers to the court of the Song dynasty.¹ Missing a title and a date, the album is known as “The Tributors” and is attributed to Li Gonglin 李公麟 (ca. 1049-1106).

The tribute bearers are from Boni 淳泥 (western Borneo), Sanfoqi 三佛齊, Fusang 扶桑, Kunlun Cengqi 崑崙層期, Nüwang guo 女王國, Huihu 回鶻 (Uighurs), Dada 韃靼 (Tatars), and Nüsong 女送.

The leaves consist of individual paintings of the tribute missions as well as a text with more information on the countries of origin. The authenticity of the work as a painting by Li Gonglin is not established. One Boni mission had arrived during the lifetime of Li Gonglin in 1082² which would suggest a date after 1082 for the origin of the painting. The identification of the accompanying text is more complicated. It mentions “the seventh day of the twelfth month as a holiday” (*yi layue qiri wei sui* 以臘月七日為歲)³ which could be a paraphrase from the entry on Boni in the *Taiping huanyuji* 太平寰宇記 (late tenth century) (*fan suizhong shier yue yi qiri wei jie* 凡歲終十二月七日為節) where the information appears for the first time.⁴ It subsequently appears in the *Zhufan zhi* 諸蕃志 (1225) as “the seventh day of the twelfth month is their spring festival” (*yi shier yue qiri wei suijie* 以十二月七日為歲節)

¹ “The Tributors”, <https://artmuseum.princeton.edu/collections/objects/44697>, accessed 16 April 2026. See also Alfreda J. Murck, “Acquisitions 1968”, *Record of the Art Museum, Princeton University* 27.2 (1968): 94.

² The mission, the second from Boni after 977, has been recorded under the second month of the fifth year of the Yuanfeng era (March 1082) in Li Tao 李燾, *Xu Zizhi tongjian changbian* 續資治通鑒長編 (Beijing: Zhonghua shuju, 1992), 323.7791. The *Song huiyao* specify the date as the 24th day in the second month of the fifth year (26 March 1082). See *Song huiyao jigao* 199, “fanyi” 7.37a (7858). The *Songshi* confirms the *Song huiyao* and records it under the day with the cyclical characters *bingzi* 丙子. See *Songshi* 16.306.

³ Note that the character *la* is incorrectly copied on the leaf.

⁴ Yue Shi 樂史, *Taiping huanyuji* (Beijing: Zhonghua shuju, 2007), 179.3437.

which is a closer fit than the *Taiping huanyuji*.⁵ If the text was copied or paraphrased from the *Zhufan zhi*, it would have been applied after the completion of the *Zhufan zhi* in 1225.

The introductory sentence on the Sanfoqi leaf, “Sanfoqi is located to the south of the ocean. It is an important maritime thoroughfare for all barbarians” (*Sanfoqi guo zai hai zhi nan wei zhufan shuidao zhi yaochong* 三佛齊國在海之南諸蕃水道之要衝) is also found in the *Lingwai daida* 嶺外代答 by Zhou Qufei 周去非 of 1178.⁶ In the middle of the text, we encounter this quite highly interesting statement:

In the heat of the summer, they often tie reeds together (*juanpu* 縛蒲) and set them up next to the water to live in them. Therefore, they take Pu 蒲 as their family name. This detail traces the name Pu that by not a few scholars starting with Friedrich Hirth (1845-1927) has been and is understood as a marker of a Muslim affiliation of the bearer⁷, to the use of a plant in the building of homes on riverbanks. Other texts including the *Lingwai daida* retain the riverside construction of houses of the local Sanfoqi population or understand it as the construction of floats.

The phrase that concerns us here is “It is their custom to construct rafts, float them on the water and live in them” (*qisu juanpai fushui er ju* 其俗縛排浮水而居). There is a chance that *pu* was the original term used as far as the *Yiyu zhi* 異域志 (c. 1300) by Zhou Zhizhong 周致中 is concerned. The relevant passage reads:

This country lies in the southern ocean. Sailing from Guangzhou straight south one can reach it in half a month. It is a main thoroughfare of all the barbarians. They build city walls from wooden planks. Many people in the country have the surname Pu. They assemble rafts to float on the water and they live on them.⁸

Lu Junling 陸峻嶺 explains in the commentary that *pu* 蒲 was replaced by *pai* 排, and that the character *ju* 居 was missing and supplemented from the parallel passages in the *Lingwai*

⁵ Zhao Rukuo 趙汝适, *Zhufan zhi jiaoshi* 諸蕃志校釋, revised and annotated by Yang Bowen 楊博文 (Beijing: Zhonghua shuju, 2000), 136.

⁶ Zhou Qufei, *Lingwai daida jiaozhu* 嶺外代答校注, revised and with commentaries by Yang Wuquan 楊武泉 (Beijing: Zhonghua shuju, 1999), 86.

⁷ Hirth, “Die Insel Hainan nach Chao Ju-kua”, in: *Festschrift für Adolf Bastian zu seinem 70. Geburtstag* (Berlin, 1896), p. 487, note 1.

⁸ Zhou Zhizhong, *Yiyuzhi*, edited by Lu Junling 陸峻嶺, in *Zhenla fengtuji jiaozhu Xiyu lu Yiyu zhi* 真臘風土記校注 西游錄 異域志 (Beijing: Zhonghua shuju, 2000), 2.41.

daida, *Zhufan zhi*⁹, and *Sancai tuhui* 三才圖繪. Interestingly, the text contained in the *Sancai tuhui* (1609) indeed has the character *ju*, but retains the character *pu* instead of *pai*.¹⁰

The above evidence may be added to the explanations of the “surname” Pu that regard it as a transcription of honorific addresses in Champa and Sanfoqi rather than a transcription of a Muslim name. It has an advantage over the latter explanation for it can be deduced from within the original source material instead of being imprinted as an interpretation not traceable anywhere in the relevant Chinese texts.

⁹ Zhao Rukuo, *Zhufan zhi jiaoshi* 諸蕃志校釋, edited by Yang Bowen 楊博文 (Beijing: Zhonghua shuju, 2000), 1.35.

¹⁰ Wang Qi 王圻, *Sancai tuhui*, (Shanghai: Shanghai guji chubanshe, 1988), 12.14a (picture), 12.14b (text).

Perhaps, then, one could understand the variant passages in the *Lingwai daida* and *Zhufan zhi* has attempts to make sense of *pu*. The modern Malay word for bamboo is *buluh* for which *pu* could be a phonetical transcription, but for lack of the necessary competence in classical Malay I cannot confirm this connection.